

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842
ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue VI, June 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala

PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 0000000000

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034400000

TIN 293-150-678 / Business Permit No. 0000000000

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2500

pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

*"Write. Connect.
Educate."*

 @pinagpalapublishing

 pinagpala_publishing

 www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Righting Model: Fostering Journalistic Skills among Student Writers

ISMAEL, JR. B. SIBAG

Master Teacher I

Mina National High School

Schools Division of Iloilo

Bangac-Talibong Grande, Mina, Iloilo

Campus journalism is valued in schools in the Philippines. To improve the journalistic skills of the student writers, the researcher created the *Righting Model*. Thus, this study aimed to ascertain the mean scores of student writers in news writing, feature writing and editorial writing before and after the intervention. This one-group pretest-posttest research utilized a researcher-made Journalistic Performance Rating Scale Checklist. Five student writers of the English publication in a public secondary school in a Mina National High School in Schools Division of Iloilo were the participants of the study. Statistical tools such as the Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test, Paired t-test, Mean and Standard Deviation were used to describe and analyze the data. All statistical computations were processed through the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software with a level of significance set at .05 alpha. Results of the study revealed that there was a significant difference in students' journalistic performance before and after the intervention which was the *Righting Model*. The level of mean scores before the intervention was Developing. After the intervention, it rose to Proficiency level. Furthermore, the results revealed that after the use of *the Righting Model*, the mean scores of student writers when the categories were paired did have significant differences. This may mean that the model applies to any journalistic category.

Keywords: Education, *Righting Model*, Journalistic Skills, Philippines

Introduction

In schools in the Philippines, both public and private, from elementary to tertiary levels, campus journalism is valued. It has turned into a laboratory for discovering and molding the journalistic talent and skills of the learners. It plays an important role in the academe as it trains learners to become responsible members of society (PEJ Reader, n.d.; Laya, Aleria, Laroya, 2013).

To enhance the journalistic skills of the student writers, the researcher created the *Righting Model*. It is a mini-workshop framework with 5Cs. Collaboration and the use of technology are highlighted in the workshop. Students involved in cooperative learning do better especially in the development of reasoning and critical thinking skills than those who

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VI (June 2024), p.265-272 International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

are not involved (Carleton, 2006). Another aspect of the workshop is technology, which has helped improve engagement and interaction with other benefits.

Methodology

Participants

The student writers of the *Riverside Echoes*, the official English publication of Mina National High School were the participants of this study for seven weeks.

Data- Gathering Instrument

In gathering data, the researcher designed a researcher-made Journalistic Performance Rating Scale Checklist validated by three experts in the field of campus journalism and was given a score of 1-Strongly Disagree, 2- Disagree, 3- Slightly Agree, 4- Agree, and 5- Strongly Agree in each guideline.

Data Collection Procedure

The validated instrument together with the pretest and posttest in news, feature and editorial writing was given to the two jurors.

To analyze and interpret data gathered before and after the intervention, the researcher used statistical treatment like mean and standard deviation.

Thereafter, the obtained data during the pretest and posttest were analyzed

Intervention

The researcher created an intervention called *Righting Model*. The framework has five steps termed 5Cs; namely, Challenge, Craft, Connect, Collaborate and Check.

Narrative of the Intervention

On Day 1 of the workshop, the researcher challenged the participants as he administered the pretest. They wrote one article for each category: news, feature and editorial. Connect, the next step in the process follows. Here, the participants watched YouTube lecture on ethics in journalism, copyright laws and how to write news. The video about news writing dealt with the characteristics of good news writers, sources of news, elements of a good news story, examples of effective news leads and structure of a good news story.

On the other hand, the video on feature writing focused on the characteristics of a good feature story, the kinds of feature articles and the structure of a good feature story. The lecture on editorial writing was on the characteristics of a good editorial, the kinds of editorial and the structure of an editorial.

The student journalists then discussed among themselves the important concepts they had learned from the YouTube lectures. Generalization with the researcher as facilitator followed.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessed M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VI (June 2024), p.265-272 International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

The next step collaborate, came next. The student writers were given five examples of a news article. They had to analyze the article one at a time collaboratively. In analyzing, they will focus on the styles and structures used by the author in writing that particular article.

After the session on news writing, a feature writing activity was done. Just like in the news writing activity, the student writers were each given five examples of feature articles. The sample feature articles are of different types. They had to analyze the article collaboratively, one at a time. In analyzing, they had to focus on the styles and structure used by the author in writing those feature articles.

A separate session for editorial activity was done following the same procedure as in news and feature activities. Every participant was given the chance to share his/her observations.

After the sessions for a group activity on analyzing the structures of good news, feature and editorial articles, another group activity followed. They were given strips of erroneous articles. Each strip contains a paragraph of the article which they had to arrange and edit, considering grammar and usage rules and mechanics based on the stylebook. This is the Crafting stage. These steps were also used in the feature and editorial which were done on separate schedules.

It is important to note that the Connect, Collaborate and Craft steps are cyclical.

For the last step in the model, which is Check, the students revisited their original articles. Individually, they rewrote the article by applying or following the structure of one of the five articles given to them.

Data Analysis Procedure

The tabulated data from the instruments administered were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. The statistical significance was set at .05. The data were subjected to the following statistical tools: mean, standard deviation, and Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test.

Mean and Standard Deviation were used to determine the mean scores of student writers in news, feature and editorial writing before and after the interventions. The paired t-test and Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test were used to determine if there was a significant difference in the mean scores of student writers before and after the intervention and in the mean scores of paired journalistic categories after the intervention.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Table 1

Mean Scores in Journalistic Skills of Students before and after the Workshop as an Entire Group

	Pretest		Posttest	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation
As Entire Group	1.711	0.590	4.389	0.269

Legend: Scale

4.51	-	5.0
3.51	-	4.5
2.51	-	3.5
1.51	-	2.5
1.0	-	1.5

Description

Advance
Proficiency
Approaching Proficiency
Developing
Beginning

Table 2

Table 2 presents the mean scores of student writers before the workshop when classified according to journalistic categories

As shown in the table, among the three journalistic categories, news writing got the highest mean ($M=1.853$). The category with the second highest mean score is Feature writing with $M=1.740$. Editorial writing got the lowest mean score which is $M=1.540$. Students' mean scores before the intervention all belong to the Developing level.

Mean Scores of Students in Journalistic Skills before the Workshop when Classified according to Journalistic Performance

Journalistic Performance	Mean Score	Standard Deviation
News Writing	1.853	0.723
Feature Writing	1.740	0.702
Editorial Writing	1.540	0.420

Table 3

Table 3 presents the mean scores of student writers after the workshop in the three journalistic categories. In news writing, student writers got a mean score of $M=4.213$. In feature writing, the mean score was $M=4.600$. On the other hand, editorial writing has a mean score of 4.353. Based on the results, after the intervention, feature writing belongs to

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

the Advance level while news writing and editorial writing both belong to the Proficiency level.

Mean Scores of Students in Journalistic Skills after the Workshop when Classified according to Journalistic Performance

Journalistic Performance	Mean Score	Standard Deviation
News Writing	4.213	0.585
Feature Writing	4.600	0.113
Editorial Writing	4.353	0.305

Inferential Data Analysis

Paired *t*-test and Wilcoxon- Signed Ranks Test were used to determine the significant difference in the mean scores of student writers before and after the intervention and among the paired journalistic categories.

Difference in Mean Scores before and after Intervention

Table 4

As reflected in Table 4, the results of the Paired *t*-test revealed that there was a significant difference between the pretest and post-test mean scores of student writers in three journalistic categories. The *t*-value is 7.150, $p=0.000$.

Paired *t*-test to Show the Significance of Differences in Journalistic Skills in the

Pretest and Posttest of the Entire Group

Test	Mean Score	<i>t</i> -value	Sig.(2-tailed)
Pretest	1.711	7.150	0.000
Posttest	4.389		

$p < .05$ Significant

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Difference in Mean Scores after the Intervention among Paired Journalistic Categories

Table 5

As reflected in Table 5, the results of the Wilcoxon- Signed Ranks Test revealed that there was no significant difference between the mean scores of student writers in news writing and feature writing ($H= 0.561$, $p=0.561$). The mean score for feature writing is 4.213 while the mean score for news writing is 4.600.

Wilcoxon- Signed Ranks Test to Show Significance of Difference in

Journalistic Skills in Feature Writing and News Writing

Journalistic Performance	Mean Score	<i>H</i>	Sig.(2-tailed)
Feature Writing	4.213	0.561	0.561
News Writing	4.600		

$p < .05$

Table 6

As reflected in Table 6, the results of the Wilcoxon- Signed Ranks Test revealed that there was no significant difference between the mean scores of student writers in news writing and feature writing ($H= 1.049$, $p=0.294$). The mean score for news writing is 4.600 while the mean score for editorial writing is 4.353.

Wilcoxon- Signed Ranks Test to Show Significance of Difference in Journalistic Skills in News Writing and Editorial Writing

Journalistic Performance	Mean Score	<i>H</i>	Sig.(2-tailed)
News Writing	4.600	1.049	0.294
Editorial Writing	4.353		

$p < .05$

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Table 7

As reflected in Table 7, the results of the Wilcoxon- Signed Ranks Test revealed that there was a significant difference between the mean scores of student writers in feature writing and editorial writing ($H= 2.365$, $p= 0.018$). The mean score for feature writing is 4.213 while the mean score for editorial writing is 4.353.

Wilcoxon- Signed Ranks Test to Show Significance of Difference in Journalistic Skills in Feature Writing and Editorial Writing

Journalistic Performance	Mean Score	<i>H</i>	Sig.(2-tailed)
Feature Writing	4.213	2.365	0.018
Editorial Writing	4.353		

$p < .05$ Significant

Conclusions

From the results of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. There was an increase in the mean scores of student writers before and after the workshop; hence, the use of the *Righting Model* seems effective.
2. Among the three categories, the use of the *Righting Model* does not show a significant difference all the time. With this, one can conclude that this model applies to any journalistic category.

Implications

The findings of the present study have led to certain implications:

1. Student writers' exposure to the *Righting Model* may have made them better writers.
2. The results of the study challenge the School Administrators and School Paper Advisers to provide opportunities to train student writers to further improve their skills.
3. The *Righting model* widens students' perspective in the field of journalism for it highlights 21st Century Skills.
4. With the use of the *Righting Model*, student journalists' social skills can be improved.
5. Finally, this newly created model develops students' genuine love for writing news, features, and editorials.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VI (June 2024), p.265-272 International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

References

Laya, Aleria, Laroya (2013) *PEJ Reader*. Retrieved from:
<https://ejournals.ph/function/reader1/read2/web/reader.php?id=uploads%2Farchive%2FUICRJ%2FVol.+19>

Why use cooperative learning? (2006). Cooperative Learning.
<https://serc.carleton.edu/introgeo/cooperative/whyuse.html>

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.12547207

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.